

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

101035819

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
1	D1.7	D7	Plan for the matchmaking event	UT

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Report	Public	D5 (D1.5) D8 (D1.8) D23 (D4.3)

Description (short)
This document describes the logic behind the organization of the ENLIGHT matchmaking event and provides a summary of the various planned sessions.

Document Version Control		
Version 0.1	Originated by:	UT
Version 0.2	Originated by:	UT after WP1 members' comments and edits
Final version	Originated by:	UT after PB members' comments and edits
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15585482	

The content of this deliverable represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains."

Contents

Introduction	3
Date and format	4
Planned sessions	4
B2match platform integration	6
Follow up	6
Appendix 1 – ENLIGHT matchmaking event programme	7
Appendix 2 – Pitching slides template	9

Introduction

ENLIGHT is a European University formed by ten comprehensive research-intensive universities from ten European countries¹ (University of the Basque Country in Spain, University of Bern in Switzerland, University of Bordeaux in France, Comenius University Bratislava in Slovakia, University of Galway in Ireland, Ghent University in Belgium, University of Göttingen in Germany, University of Groningen in the Netherlands, University of Tartu in Estonia, Uppsala University in Sweden).

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Science With and For Society (SwafS) work programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance.

One of the key aims of the ENLIGHT RISE project is to promote cooperation between alliance researchers. In December 2023, an amendment to shift from the development of the digital matching tool for ENLIGHT researchers to the organization of the matchmaking event was approved by the EC, changing the content of this deliverable from the tool development plan to the description of the event. Following the amendment approval, we have prepared an event programme to allow ENLIGHT researchers to present their ideas for building joint projects. Furthermore, we have included sessions on future opportunities for researcher collaboration within ENLIGHT 2.0 and on the tools developed within RISE that can interest ENLIGHT researchers. To promote synergies and improve visibility, we have co-scheduled the WP4 event for early career researchers with the matchmaking event. Finally, we have integrated a digital component into the event by setting up a dedicated b2match page, which will remain available after the event.

In many ways, the ENLIGHT Matchmaking Event serves as a link and transition between the ENLIGHT RISE (Horizon2020 SwafS) project and the ENLIGHT 2.0 (Erasmus+) project. This is evidenced not only by the fact that we will use the event to promote upcoming ENLIGHT 2.0 instruments but also by including the University of Bern researchers and adding the Culture and Creativity focus area² as one of the pitching sessions. The event will also help us strengthen the overall position of research within the alliance as partners aim to collaborate across all areas. In what follows, we present the logic behind the event format, timing, and content. As a follow-up to the event, we

¹ ENLIGHT has expanded to formally include the University of Bern with the start of ENLIGHT 2.0.

² This is a new focus area for the alliance added with the start of ENLIGHT 2.0.

plan to ask participants to fill in a feedback questionnaire to reflect on the usefulness of similar events in the future.

Date and format

Initially, we had planned to organize the matchmaking event in person in Tartu towards the end of April or in May, allowing sufficient time for preparations. However, considering potential challenges with accommodation due to Tartu being the European Cultural Capital this year, we also explored a hybrid option or relocating the event to Tallinn.

Eventually, since the internal negotiations took longer than expected due to the importance of the amendment in question, it became impractical to organize a large-scale in-person event in Estonia upon final approval of the amendment. This was mainly due to logistical constraints, making it difficult for a significant number of researchers to travel to Estonia (Tallinn or Tartu) on short notice. Furthermore, with Tartu designated as the 2024 European Cultural Capital, venues and accommodations had already become unavailable, adding to the challenge of the event organization.

The timing also posed obstacles to organizing the event in person. Based on partner schedules, considering school holidays and the beginning of the exam period in mid-May in many countries, the only possible dates to accommodate most partners were April 29 and April 30. At this stage, we considered organizing a hybrid event with researchers participating online and the ENLIGHT RISE R&I Support Group coming together in Tartu. In the end, we decided against this as May 1 is a day off in many countries, and a hybrid format would introduce additional complications to the logistics of the event; environmental effects of such travel were also considered. Therefore, we locked in April 29-30 for the online matchmaking event. A further benefit of this approach is the potential to reach a wider audience of researchers, boosting ENLIGHT's visibility. Our original estimates were that we could bring around 60 participants to Tartu (researchers and research support staff). With the active promotion of the event, we can hope that more participants will attend various sessions online.

Planned sessions

The core of the matchmaking event will take place on April 29. The day will start with an opening session with several presentations about ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT 2.0. Firstly, we will provide an overview of the ENLIGHT alliance, its focus, and achievements, as well as briefly introduce ENLIGHT 2.0. This can be especially useful for researchers who are not very familiar with ENLIGHT yet. We will then move to present the upcoming

opportunities and (recently opened) calls for researchers and academics in ENLIGHT 2.0, such as ENLIGHT Incubator Grants, ENLIGHT Thematic Networks, ENLIGHT+³ and ENLIGHT AIM Days. Finally, we will introduce the pitching sessions that will follow and the matchmaking platform⁴ (see below).

The session described above will be followed by pitching sessions for setting up research collaborations within ENLIGHT. Researchers who are looking for partners to establish an ENLIGHT Thematic Network, submit a joint funding proposal or start a joint project will pitch their ideas to other ENLIGHT researchers. There will be two pitching sessions, each with 3 parallel breakout rooms dedicated to the ENLIGHT challenge areas. Session one includes Health and wellbeing, Culture and creativity and Climate change, and session two is dedicated to Digitalization and digital revolution, Equity and Energy and circular economy. The sessions were organized in a way that researchers who may be interested in overlapping challenge areas could attend both. Pitches are expected to be up to 5 minutes, based on the provided pitching slides template, followed by 5 minutes of questions from the audience. ENLIGHT RISE R&I-SG/WP1 members will help moderate pitching sessions. One concern in relation to the pitching sessions is that there will not be enough interest from the researchers due to conflicting responsibilities or last-minute changes of plans; if issues arise, we will adjust the pitching sessions accordingly before the event starts. The matchmaking component will be supported by the dedicated b2match platform where registered ENLIGHT researchers will be able to arrange one-on-one meetings following the event, which will give researchers more time and flexibility in reaching out to their peers.

The final session on April 29 will be dedicated to the selected tools that we have developed in RISE that can be of use to ENLIGHT researchers. This will include demonstration of the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory,⁵ which can be used to find potential collaboration partners within ENLIGHT; ENLIGHT Impact Repository⁶ and ENLIGHT Open Science toolkit.⁷ We will also remind our researchers about the support officers' network that can be used for finding partners for joint projects.

While the event on April 29 is open to all interested researchers, the April 30 programme is focused on early career researchers (ECRs) in collaboration with WP4. This event represents the 3rd networking event for ECRs with a focus on leadership

³ <https://enlight-eu.org/index.php/university-about-us/news-events/158-news/1095-prepare-calls-2024>.

⁴ <https://www.b2match.com/e/enlight-rise>.

⁵ <https://observatory.enlight-eu.org/>.

⁶ <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/>.

⁷ <https://enlight-eu.org/index.php/landing-research-and-innovation/open-science/1016-enlight-open-science-toolkit>.

skills. Juko-Mart Kõlar from the University of Tartu will conduct a workshop that will present a practical case study on navigating the complexities of building and managing a diverse team in a fiercely competitive landscape. He will outline strategies and techniques for fostering an environment where every team member comprehends their role in achieving objectives and where efficient coordination mechanisms are ingrained in the daily culture. As part of, ECRs will have an opportunity to network between each other exploring options for further collaboration.

B2match platform integration

As mentioned above, the matchmaking event will be supported by the dedicated [b2match platform](#). The platform serves the purpose of participant registration for the April 29 event, it will contain links to join the various sessions, and importantly will support the matchmaking element of the event allowing researchers to set up one-on-one meetings to discuss potential collaboration in detail. Furthermore, the platform has a [dedicated section](#) for posting various funding opportunities relevant to the ENLIGHT challenge areas (by R&I support staff) and collaboration offers/requests by partners. The section is only visible to the registered participants, just as the list of participants and event links. The platform will remain operational after the event until the end of Jan 2025. This will allow for continuous engagement of our researchers.

Follow up

The matchmaking event will allow us to present multiple tools and upcoming opportunities to ENLIGHT researchers to ensure uptake and engagement. After the event, we will collect feedback from participants to evaluate the usefulness of the event, and in particular the pitching sessions, to assess if there can be interest in similar events in the future. We will also monitor the use of the b2match platform following the event. As it introduces the digital component to the matchmaking in ENLIGHT, it could provide insights into whether the consortium should invest in a more permanent digital solution for researcher matchmaking.

Appendix 1 – ENLIGHT matchmaking event programme

ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

ENLIGHT Matchmaking Events

Monday, April 29, 2024 – ENLIGHT Tools and Pitching Sessions for Joint Applications and Projects

09:00-10:00 CET Welcome and opening (*plenary session*)

- Welcome from the University of Tartu Vice-Rector for Research Prof Mari Moora
- Overview of ENLIGHT: consortium, achievements, ENLIGHT 2.0
- Opportunities for researchers within ENLIGHT
- Intro of the pitching sessions and matchmaking platform

10:00-10:30 CET Break

10:30-12:00 CET Parallel pitching sessions per ENLIGHT focus area:

- Health and wellbeing
- Culture and creativity
- Climate change

12:00-13:00 CET Break

13:00-14:30 CET Parallel pitching sessions per ENLIGHT focus area:

- Digitalization and digital revolution
- Equity
- Energy and circular economy

14:30-15:00 CET Break

15:00-16:00 CET ENLIGHT RISE tools and summary of the day (*plenary session*)

- R&I Observatory
- Open Science toolkit
- Impact tools
- Wrap-up

Tuesday, April 30, 2024 – Leadership Training and Networking for Early Career Researchers

10:00-11:00 CET Session I of leadership training and networking for ECRs

11:00-11:30 CET Break

11:30-12:30 CET Session II of leadership training and networking for ECRs

12:30-13:30 CET Lunch break

13:30-14:30 CET Session III of leadership training and networking for ECRs

Appendix 2 – Pitching slides template

ENLIGHT MATCHMAKING EVENTS 29.04.2024

université
BORDEAUX

CORE IDEA

- Core idea:
- Why is this important:
- Are you looking for partners to submit a proposal, create an ETN etc.?

REQUIRED EXPERTISE

- What expertise do you have:
- What expertise are you looking for:
- Access to data:

CONTACT INFO

- Name:
- University:
- Email: